

How to complete the template to compile food additive usage level data for Pullulan (E 1204)

How to complete the 'AddUseLevTemplate_PULLULAN' template:

This file is designed for inputting usage level data on the food additive Pullulan. It maintains the structure of the previous additive usage level template but without macros.

By placing your mouse on the column headings in the template, you can view a brief description of the item to be reported. Columns headed in red are the mandatory to complete, orange headed columns are recommended while blue columns are optional.

The maximum number of records that can be inputted in the template is 500. If you have more than 500 results to send to EFSA please input these in an additional file.

For each data element in the template, please find below a brief description of the information needed.

1. **Sample ID (AD.01): Mandatory field.** Please enter a **unique** identification code for each sample. The unique identification code cannot exceed 20 characters and special characters must be avoided. For this call the examples below shows how to report for 3 records: where E 1204 is the E number for Pullulan, ABC is the abbreviation/acronym of the data provider followed by a sequential number

Sample ID (AD.01)
E1204_ABC_01
E1204_ABC_02
E1204_ABC_03

2. **Country of reporting (AD.02): Optional field.** Indicate in which European country your product is available by choosing the country name from the drop-down list. If your product is available in six or more European countries, please use "European Union". If your product is available typically only in a certain region, you can report more than one country in this field by selecting the relevant country names. For example, if your product is available in the Scandinavian region, you can choose all the relevant Scandinavian countries from the drop-down list.
3. **EFSA Product code (AD.03): Mandatory field.** This column and the next column 'EFSA Product Code Text' are completed by clicking on the drop-down list in the column 'EFSA Product Code Text' (column D). A list of reportable food items in which Pullulan can be used will appear. Select the food that most closely matches the food you are reporting

on. The corresponding EFSA code will appear in the adjacent column 'EFSA Product code (AD.03)' as shown in the example below

C	D
FSA Product Code (AD.03)	EFSA Product Code Text
.01.001311	Candies, with sugar

In case you cannot find the exact description of food you want to report on please select the closest match as a full description of the food Pullulan is used in must be provided in **Product full text description (AD.05)**.

- Food category (AD.04): Mandatory field.** Please choose the additive food category from the drop-down list as shown in the figure below.

E	F
Food category (AD.04)	Food category LL (AD.04B)
<div style="border: 1px solid gray; padding: 2px;"> 05.2 Other confectionery including breath refreshing microsv 05.2.1 Other confectionery with added sugar 05.2.2 Other confectionery without added sugar 07 Food supplements as defined in Directive 2002/46/EC exclud 07.1 Food supplements supplied in a solid form including capsu 07.2 Food supplements supplied in a liquid form </div>	

- Food category LL (AD.04B): Recommended field.** Use the drop-down list to fully describe the additive food category from the exemptions/restrictions in the Regulation (EC) No 1333/2008 (amended).
- Product full text description (AD.05): Mandatory field.** The food item can be fully specified with free text up to maximum of 250 characters. This is very important as it provides more information about the product than that available in the EFSA product code field.
- Consumption index (AD.06): Optional field:** This field can be used to report if the product is a 'Niche product' or 'Widely consumed'.
- Is it a food formulated for infants (<12 months) (AD.06B): Optional field:** Report either 'Yes' or 'No'.
- Brand name (AD.07): Optional field.** Free text field to indicate the food brand.
- Manufacturer (AD.08): Optional field.** Free text field to indicate the food manufacturer.
- Year of reporting (AD.09): Mandatory field.** Provide the reporting year, this should be the year of the additive use – usually the current year that is 2022.

12. **Result code (AD.10): Mandatory field.** The code is automatically generated for each record by concatenating the 'Sample ID' and 'Parameter code'.
13. **Parameter code text selection (AD.13): Mandatory field.** Only 'Pullulan' is available: this selection automatically completes the code in 'Parameter code' (AD.11) and 'Parameter E-code' (AD.12).
14. **Parameter text (AD.14) Optional field.** EFSA would like to know if other additives are used in the food in addition to Pullulan. Please indicate the E number(s).
15. **Usage unit (AD.15): Mandatory field.** provide the unit of measurement for the additive. If there is a maximum permitted limit defined, the MPL value and the usage values should be provided in the same unit.
16. **Usage level minimum (AD.16) Optional field - Usage level typical (AD.17) Mandatory field- Usage level maximum (AD.18): Optional field** Please provide the minimum, the typical and the maximum usage level of the additive. **It is mandatory to report the typical usage level.**
17. **Is maximum permitted level defined (AD.19): Mandatory field.** please indicate whether there is a maximum permitted level (MPL) defined for the additive in legislation or if added as Quantum satis. If the MPL is defined the MPL value must be indicated in the '**Is maximum permitted level defined**' (AD.20) field.
18. **Function of food additive (AD.21): Mandatory field.** Describe the function of the food additive by choosing from the drop-down list of additive functions.
19. **Percentage of moisture in the original sample (AD.22): Optional field.** If the Expression of the result is expressed as dry weight indicate the percentage of moisture as a number.
20. **Percentage of fat in the original sample (AD.23): Optional field.** If the Expression of the result is expressed as fat weight indicate the percentage of fat as a number.
21. **Expression of the result (AD.24): Mandatory field.** please describe whether the results have been expressed in whole weight (as consumed), dry weight or fat weight.
22. **Conversion/Dilution factor (AD.25): Optional field.** Complete to indicate the recommended conversion or dilution factor if this applies to food before it is consumed.
23. **Comment of the result (AD.26): Optional field** Comments on the reported results can be provided in this field up to a maximum of 250 characters.
24. **Columns AB-AH:** check and validate your entered data. If there is any issue, e.g. one of the free text fields contains more characters, than the maximum allowed 250, or the reported unit is incorrect, the cell becomes red.

Once you have inputted your data, send the completed file to:

data.collection@efsa.europa.eu